

EFEKTIVITAS LKPD BERBASIS *BLENDED LEARNING* BERBANTUAN MULTIMEDIA INTERAKTIF UNTUK MELATIH VISUAL SPASIAL PESERTA DIDIK

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mengetahui keefektifan Lembar Kerja Peserta Didik (LKPD) berbasis *blended learning* berbantuan multimedia interaktif dalam melatih kemampuan visual spasial peserta didik pada materi Ikatan Kovalen. Metode penelitian menggunakan *one group pretest-posttest design* dengan melakukan uji coba terbatas pada peserta didik Jurusan Kimia Analisis SMK Negeri 1 Cerme Gresik yang dipilih berdasarkan kemampuan peserta didik dari kemampuan rendah, sedang, dan tinggi sebanyak 15 orang. *Pretest* dan *posttest* digunakan sebagai instrumen untuk mengetahui kemampuan visual spasial peserta didik. Data dianalisis secara deskriptif kuantitatif. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa data *pretest* dan *posttest* berdistribusi normal dan hasil rata-rata *N-Gain* pada kategori tinggi sehingga disimpulkan bahwa LKPD berbasis *blended learning* berbantuan multimedia interaktif dalam melatih kemampuan visual spasial peserta didik pada materi Ikatan Kovalen efektif sebagai bahan ajar.

Kata Kunci: ikatan kovalen; LKPD berbasis *blended learning*; visual spasial.

Abstract

The research aimed to determine the effectiveness of the Student Worksheet (LKPD) based on *blended learning* assisted by interactive multimedia in training students' visual-spatial skills in the Covalent Bond material. The research method used a *one group pretest-posttest design* by conducting a limited trial on students of the Analytical Chemistry Department at SMK Negeri 1 Cerme Gresik who were selected based on the ability of students from low, medium, and high abilities as many as 15 people. *Pretest* and *posttest* are used as instruments to determine the visual-spatial ability of students. Data were analyzed descriptively quantitatively. The results showed that the *pretest* and *posttest* data were normally distributed with the average *N-Gain* in the high category, so it can be concluded that the LKPD based on *blended learning* assisted by interactive multimedia in training students' visual-spatial abilities on the Covalent Bond material is effective as teaching material.

Keywords: covalent bonding; LKPD-based *blended learning*; visual spatial.